

ISSUES OF CRIME PREVENTION AMONG WOMEN

Sevinova Dilabza Ghulomovna

Abstract:

All types of crime are dangerous and harmful to humanity. For this reason, from time immemorial, heavy punishment was applied to those who committed theft and murder, the goal was that the people should learn from this and that no one would repeat it. Women's crime today is more dangerous than men's crime. It is not about the amount of damage caused to the victim, but about the family of the criminal woman, the future she will bring up. In this article, the author expresses his opinion.

Keywords:

Offense, crime, women, socio-political, victim, children, environment, society, anti-social, women, damage, spirituality, future, children.

Today, creating a healthy social environment in society is one of the urgent issues. As noted, women's finding their place in the family and society, active participation in the social and political life of the country largely depends on the existing conditions in our country and the support provided to them. In this regard, not only the support of women's initiatives and comprehensive protection of their rights, but also the issue of crime prevention among them is considered urgent. In this regard, the issue of studying and eliminating the factors that cause women's antisocial behavior is in the focus of attention of the structures involved in ensuring gender equality.

It is difficult to fully express how difficult and difficult it is to receive the name "criminal". Because when we hear this word, our flesh trembles, we say "God forbid". Can we imagine a woman who is a mother, a sister, a beloved wife

in front of us, behind bars as a criminal? There are also those who, regardless of their actions, are drowning in the mire of various vices and crimes by tarnishing the holy name of a woman.

The concept of "feminine crime" arose in the 20th century and was considered a part of general crime and committed by men.

psychologically, biologically and physiologically different from committed crimes. Jurisprudence shows that crimes against women, which are statistically common worldwide, include theft, fraud, embezzlement and drug trafficking, prostitution, and murder. There is a common feature in the commission of this type of crime by female criminals, and according to many criminologists, the tendency to commit this type of crime is related to the fact that it is subjectively easier for female criminals. For example, crimes such as theft, fraud, embezzlement, and embezzlement require more mental activity than physical labor. Instead, the psyche of criminal women encourages them to invent various tricks to achieve an easy life, to look for new ways to evade the law, and to use their own methods of committing crimes. Also, the emotional state of a female criminal makes it possible to subjectively and objectively distinguish the crime committed by them from the crime committed by a male criminal. Only 22.8 percent of women held in places of deprivation of liberty have families. Among the criminals who killed their newborn child, there are the least number of married women. It should be mentioned that the majority of women sentenced to prison (67.7%) have children, and every fourth woman has two or more children. There are many single mothers among them.

Feminine crime is a set of crimes committed by women. Women's crime is a part of crime, which is characterized by a number of qualitative and quantitative characteristics, the uniqueness of a number of personality traits that determine the factors of criminality. Accordingly, the prevention of women's crime also has its

own characteristics. The percentage of women in the total number of criminals is small, about 15%. At the same time, the structure of women's crime differs from men's crime, mainly due to the increase in mercenary crimes related to professional activities: theft by embezzlement or embezzlement, theft, fraud and other crimes against property.

In recent years, this is due to the increase in crimes in the field of economic activity, as well as the professional activities of female criminals: illegal banking, tax evasion with an organization that illegally obtained loans, illegal business. At the same time, the proportion of women's crimes in this category is much higher compared to the proportion of men's crimes. The high criminal activity of women in committing these crimes is often explained by the fact that these criminal acts occur in feminized sectors of the economy, such as trade, banking, domestic services, and money relations. In many cases, a woman's criminality is influenced by the environment that surrounds her. For example, the lack of a permanent job, low monthly salary, financial situation that does not allow for cultural recreation, constant shortages are the factors that lead women to crime. Among the most basic reasons

include emotional trauma, alcohol abuse, and personal enmity. Two different theories are put forward by scientists in the study of women's crime personality: according to A. Kettle, women's entry into the world of crime is caused by the social environment in which they lived, lifestyle, chosen profession, age, education and other general circumstances. . The external environment that surrounds him serves only as an incentive to commit a crime, the scientist says.

The composition of female crime is characterized by a relatively low level of violent crimes, which mainly occur in family and everyday life. At the same time, it should be noted that the number of such violent crimes among women has

been increasing in recent years: in most cases, they include threats of minor health damage, beatings, and murder. Despite the fact that the crime of violence against women is mainly of a family and domestic nature, in recent years there has been an increase in cases of murder of women for mercenary purposes, related to robbery. In recent years, the criminal activity of women in crimes related to drug trafficking has increased; at the same time, they often act as organizers of such crimes committed by a group of individuals. In general, the percentage of women who commit crimes is low: in 2020, it was about 15.5%. Research shows that more than half of female offenders are 30 and older. Among the women of this group, there are many single women, as evidenced by the breakdown of family ties and the death of parents. At the same time, scientists note an increase in the percentage of elderly and even elderly criminals, as well as disabled people of groups I and II. About equal numbers of women were married and unmarried at the time of the crime. At the same time, the type of punishment imposed on a woman has a great impact on the further preservation of the family. Regarding the level of education of female criminals, the situation is as follows: currently, there is a slight increase in the number of prisoners with secondary and higher education (including incomplete). And this means that women have their specialty at the time of the crime. Despite this trend, about 25% of convicted women do not have complete general education.

Various measures are taken to protect the rights and interests of women and girls. A system of issuing protection warrants to women and girls has been established. The interests of women and girls have been raised to the level of state policy. In the Decree No. PF-87 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 7, 2020, the following issues are paid close attention;

In Uzbekistan, within the framework of "National goals and tasks in the field of sustainable development until 2030", one of the priority goals is "Ensuring gender equality and expanding the rights and opportunities of all

women".

In 2022 - 2026, the National Program for increasing the activity of women in all aspects of the country's economic, political and social life (hereinafter referred to as the National Program) outlines the main directions of the state policy for supporting women. defines.

The national program considers women's rights as an integral part of human rights, and it is a set of measures for comprehensive support of women based on the principle of "For human dignity".

The purpose of the national program is to further strengthen the system of social protection of women, to strengthen their health, to create the necessary conditions for girls' education, to educate talented and educated girls and to increase their scientific potential, to protect the rights and legal interests of women. improvement of the legal basis of protection, increase of socio-economic and political activity of women, strengthening of their role in society, especially in state management, and ensuring gender equality.

The following main tasks were defined in the implementation of the national program:

- improvement of the legal framework for all-round support for women;
- implementation of comprehensive measures aimed at achieving gender equality, increasing socio-economic and political activity of women;
- creating additional conditions for women's education and involving them widely in the field of science;
- strengthen women's health, motherhood and childhood protection measures;
- prevention of harassment and violence among women and victims of human trafficking;
- socio-economic support of women detained in penal institutions, who have gone abroad, working in state and public organizations and in the private sector,

and to further strengthen the protection of their legal interests;

further improvement of comprehensive support measures for women in need of social protection;

honoring enlightened mothers, using their knowledge and rich life experience to strengthen families, raising girls' education and spiritual outlook, as well as creating conditions for their cultural recreation;

to strengthen the institution of the family, to ensure the stability of a healthy and spiritual environment in families by promoting universal and national values;

early prevention of crime and offenses among women, taking measures to increase their sense of involvement in legal culture and large-scale reforms implemented in our country.

As you have witnessed, a number of systematic works are being carried out in our country to prevent crime among women. First of all, what caused a woman to enter this path before we labeled her as a criminal? What is the solution? Didn't the people in the society cause him to acquire this evil? we need to find a solution to the questions and understand the essence of the problem more deeply.

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